

Assessing the Quality of the Library Facilities, Resources and Services: Leading Towards Quality Educational Experience

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Abstract

The library is the heart of an educational institution's knowledge repository. Hence, it provides an essential support service to the teaching-learning process and research works. Hence, this study assessed the quality of the University of Cebu library facilities, resources, and services and how it leads towards providing quality educational experience among the target-end users.

This investigation used the descriptive-survey research design using a researcher-made survey questionnaire consisting of three (3) parts. This investigation was conducted at the University of Cebu-Banilad with 382 research respondents who were officially enrolled in the various programs of the university of Cebu-Banilad for the 1st semester, 2022-2023. Treatment of data used

frequency count, simple percentage, weighted mean, and One-Way ANOVA.

The results revealed that most of the research respondents were 18 to 20 years old, females, and enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management (BSTM) program. Moreover, they assessed that the quality of personnel customer service, facilities, services, and resources of the University of Cebu-Banilad Library Department was moderately satisfactory. Therefore, the ideal standards of how the library should suffice the learning needs of the University students have a gap with the current state. So there should be regular mechanisms for updating the library as the central nerve of learning in an educational institution so that they could respond positively to the needs of 21st-century students amid the

presence of technology and digital library resources and databases.

Keywords: *Library science, quality of services, facilities & resources, descriptive, University of Cebu-Banilad*

INTRODUCTION

In universities, the three significant infrastructures are laboratories, classrooms, and libraries containing rich and balanced information resources, including equipment supporting teaching, learning, and research work. The university library is seen as the heart of the university because the library can stand on its own, but the university cannot stand on its own (Ajibero, 2004). Hence, the academic library has been described as the "heart" of the learning community, providing a place for students and faculty to research and advance their knowledge (Simmons & Andaleeb, 2001).

Moreover, the library is considered a service institution that serves its users by providing numerous resources, activities, and services to fulfill users' information needs. It is a service center supplying various kinds of information (Weinstein & McFarlane, 2017). So the librarians and library staff provide numerous services to these users, addressing their diverse needs, characteristics, and interests (Simmons & Andaleeb, 2001).

The very purpose of any library is to supply relevant and up-to-date resources to satisfy the information needs of users (Abraham & Sabu, 2022). The academic library aims at satisfying the information requirements of users. Managing information and insights, adapting to new desires of users, employing highly skilled and educated staff, surpassing competitors, and leveraging technology and social networking are the five activities to be implemented instantly in a library to succeed in modern times (Weinstein & McFarlane, 2017).

When the library features a clear understanding of user needs and the resources and materials needed, there will be accurate and timely decisions on the part of library administrators and management (Abraham & Sabu, 2022). Igben (1993) explained that a library is most functional if the services provided correspond closely with the information needs of its users.

Despite the widespread integration of electronic resources into scholarly pursuits, most college and university faculty continue to utilize traditional print publications. Nearly nine of ten (87%) faculty surveyed reported using print materials from their school's library during the preceding twelve months. This being the case, it is clear that electronic databases and article indexes have become integral to the scholarly pursuits of college and university faculty. More than four of every five respondents (83%) have used digital resources during the past year (Dickenson, 2006).

However, with the advent of online catalogs, CD-ROMs, online databases, other electronic resources, new methods of document delivery, and access to information, the role of the academic library has begun to change. Students can be physically present in the library in order to access the library's resources. With the Internet and the availability of new technologies and numerous indexes, abstracts, and databases, the range of services that academic libraries can provide has increased dramatically. Users can access the libraries' resources without stepping into the library building. They can also easily access other library resources, such as online catalogs and unrestricted databases. The Internet has opened the resources of libraries to students and faculty worldwide (Simmons & Andaleeb, 2001).

Today's academic libraries are confronted with challenges on several fronts: Mega bookstores, online information providers, multimedia products, document delivery services, and other competitive sources of information are apparently threatening their role and even their very survival (White & Abels, 1995; Herson & Altman, 1996).

Providing quality services in academic libraries is now a significant issue among academic librarians; they see the library more in terms of the provision of and access to service quality than as just a physical place. Technology and automation have also changed the way people perceive libraries. As a result, the role of libraries and librarians is also changing. Librarians have been re-evaluating their role, as reflected in many (discussions and papers). They emphasize providing good library service as more important to the user than the mere physical library building. This perspective is evident in several recent studies (Edwards & Browne, 1995; White & Abels, 1995).

Wells (1995) states that the effectiveness of libraries has often been measured by the volume of library materials available to clients, the amount of use of services and resources, and the apparent or quantified satisfaction of clients.

Iwhiwhu and Okorodudu (2012) stated that users' satisfaction with library information resources and services is a way to judge the adequacy of the library information resources and services rendered to them and if their expectations are provided them. Library user satisfaction implies how users feel after using the information resources and services and their willingness to return to the library when they need information (Ikenwe & Adegbilero-Iwari, 2014). Ijiekhuamhen et al. (2015) opined that the level of using the library depends on users' satisfaction with the available information resources and services rendered to them.

Tiemo and Ateboh (2016) investigated users' satisfaction with library information resources and services at the College of Health Sciences (CHS) library Niger Delta University, Nigeria. The results show that library users were dissatisfied with the following library information resources: reference materials in their subject areas were not up to date, national and international journals because they were also not up to date, inadequate books on the shelves, adequate project and thesis collection in the library, electronic resources such as CD ROMs were not comprehensive, library bulletin and newsletters, subscription of online databases were not regular and inadequate online database resources in their different subject areas.

Ikolo (2015) examined users' satisfaction with the library services of Delta State University Library and discovered that library users were not satisfied with reference services, inter-library loan services, electronic database services, photocopying services, bindery services, weekend library services, book lending services, CD-ROM services and indexing and abstracting services. It was also seen that library users wanted more from the existing textbooks available on shelves, internet services, newspapers/magazines, journals, and the inability to borrow books from the library. However, they were satisfied with the working hours of the library and thesis/dissertation services.

Competitive pressures, information availability, rising costs, and an increasingly aware and selective student population mandate that academic libraries become more user-focused. This calls for a better understanding of library users' specific needs to provide the appropriate type and level of service that meets those needs. This study proposes and tests a five-factor model to explain user satisfaction with academic libraries (Andaleeb & Simmonds, 1998).

Historically, academic libraries have strived to provide excellent services to their constituencies of students, faculty, and staff. In the past, library administrators had a good understanding of their library users' populations (Posey, 2009). Few studies have investigated the psychometric property of new instruments developed locally to assess students' library experience, such as their behavior, perception, and attitude toward library use (Scoulas et al., 2021).

The rapid change in technology, the emergence of modern tools used in library operations, and the demands for online access to library resources and technologies placed pressure to academic libraries since it calls for a need catch to address the evolving end-user needs. Based on experience, the failure to provide quality library resources and services would lead users' to dissatisfaction.

Also, with increased emphasis on using evidence-based data for decision-making and the pressure often felt within academic libraries to demonstrate their value, libraries must understand users' needs and seek feedback for improvement. One popular assessment tool to achieve this goal is user surveys. Academic libraries have used either standardized surveys (e.g., LibQUAL+, Ithaca S + R) or locally developed surveys (Scoulas et al., 2021). Changing the mindset of librarians, college administrators, and teaching staff is a

long-term commitment that continues to demand innovative interventions (Lugya, 2018). Therefore, this investigation aims to assess the quality of the University of Cebu library facilities, resources, and services and how it leads towards providing quality educational experience among the target end users.

FRAMEWORK

The Service Quality Model or SERVQUAL Model was developed and implemented by the American marketing gurus Valeri Zeithaml, A. Parasuraman, and Leonard Berry in 1988. It is a method to capture and measure the service quality experienced by customers. Initially, the emphasis was on the development of quality systems in the field of product quality. Over time, it became more and more essential to improve the quality of related services. Improved service quality could give organizations a competitive edge (Tools Hero, 2022).

A model of service quality is developed, which includes three groups of service quality components: physical and procedural, behavioral, and judgmental (Hayword-Farmer, 1988). The significance of various service quality dimensions differs depending on the type of service (Pollack, 2009).

Wang and Shieh (2005) discoursed that service quality has five dimensions: tangibles, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, and empathy. Overall service quality has a significantly positive effect on overall user satisfaction. Among these five dimensions, except responsiveness, all significantly positively affect overall user satisfaction. In addition, the top five crucial service quality features ranked by users are: collections, loaning and returning service, the overall atmosphere, the electronic database system, and online reservation and renewal.

A firm, in order to compete successfully, must have an understanding of consumer perception of the quality and the way service quality is influenced. Managing perceived service quality means that the firm has to match the expected service and perceived service to each other so that consumer satisfaction is achieved (Pollack, 2009).

New ways to evaluate libraries are needed. The SERVQUAL is a diagnostic tool to measure service quality, defined as the difference between customer perceptions and service expectations (Nitecki, 1996).

The library plays a significant role in any higher education center that provides formation services, resources, and facilities to support its clients in their systematic studies and research activities (Acharya & Kumara, 2022). The library is a growing organism. The success of a library depends on its resources, facilities, services, and capacity to decrease the gap between the provided and demanded information resources and services (Abraham & Sabu, 2022). Several factors influenced user satisfaction, including responsiveness, competence, assurance which translated to demeanor), tangibles, and resources (Andaleeb & Simmonds, 1998).

Olanokun and Salisu (1985) described the library as the nerve center of an educational institution and a place where information is provided to serve all patrons irrespective of their ages, political and ethical background, religion, sex, etc. The role of universities can only be achieved with a library that is adequately equipped with printed materials, information and communication technology and its related facilities, well-trained staff, and a high level of services to users that will satisfy their information needs. Also, Dhawan (n.d.) said that the libraries in adult education setups are, by design, small budget libraries, confined to one room space, and adult education staff manages them manually on a part-time basis.

Resource strategy is essential because academic library users frequent their libraries to find solutions to their academic problems and needs. In today's dynamic environment of information availability, resources do not mean only the size of a library's collections but also include a variety of other resources that, to the users, make access to information the key to judging resource adequacy. Consequently, academic librarians must continuously monitor the academic environment to provide customer-focused services. That means remaining connected to their academic institution's curriculum, teachers' resource needs and research agenda, student preference for how the needed information is packaged (i.e., CD-ROMS, journals, microfiche, audiovisuals, Internet, etc.), and related administrative use of information (e.g., career planning

and development, etc.). Librarians can play a proactive role by forging partnership relationships with their academic communities and developing various information access options, jointly selecting options that meet cost and efficacy criteria (Andaleeb & Simmonds, 1998).

Services provided by the library to online students can include instruction on how to access and use library materials; reference services to provide quick and in-depth answers to student questions; and materials delivery services that provide students with access to library materials online or items delivered to students' homes. These are Services provided by the library to the users. This can include instructions on how to access and use library materials. The Library services or facilities include Circulation Service, Reference Service, Online reservation of books, Recommendation of library material, Current Awareness Service, Inter Library Loan Service, Photocopying / Printing Service, Orientation and Information Sessions, Selective Dissemination of Information, Audio Visual Service, and Multimedia Section (IGI Global, n.d.).

Improvement and innovation for adequate access and retrieval of e-library resources are needed in information literacy training for academic researchers, search engines to index sources, comprehensive indexing of impact factor local journals, creation of metadata standards for description of digital contents, development of more comprehensive institutional repositories, development of metrics for evaluating impact factor contents for local publications, development of online user guideline for accessing e-resources, provision of usage statistics for online content, identification of free online articles in e-journals and improved user interfaces for accessing library-surfaced content constituted, building an index from a document collection to searchable data structure to enhance electronic information retrieval, developing improved descriptive metadata to describe information that is in formats other than text (e.g., image, map, animation, etc. (Anyim, n.d.).

Dickenson (2006) reported that more than three out of every five faculty members (61%) reported that the library had assisted students in finding appropriate information for assignments and projects. A slim majority of those surveyed (53%) also indicated that their library had helped students by providing access to specific course materials (e.g., traditional and electronic reserves). Nearly half (47%) indicated that their library had supported their teaching objectives by providing students with skills to refine their research papers, projects, and presentations, while a similar proportion (46%) felt that their instructional goals had been supported by library instruction (Anyim, 2018).

The essence of libraries is to satisfy the needs of their users by providing information resources and services that meet the university program curriculum (Tiemo & Ateboh, 2016). Likewise, Zeithman and Bitmar (2000) explained user satisfaction as how users determine that a product or service meets the required needs and expectations. If the products or services meet their needs or expectations, it is therefore assumed that they are satisfied with the product or services.

There was a body of research supporting the view that school libraries can positively impact academic achievement, particularly at the primary and early secondary level, and with appropriate action to ensure the service delivery is efficient and effective. However, much of this evidence was from countries where school librarians also have teaching training. More research would be needed to determine the extent to which the evidence is transferable. There is limited but significant research demonstrating the view that school libraries have the potential to impact the broader aspects of learning, including vulnerable or special needs students. Where there is evidence of impact on learning, there are associated key factors of collection levels, library staffing levels, and collaboration between the librarian and teacher. Training of teachers and librarians is demonstrated to raise mutual understanding's contribution and roles within the school library setting. Training should include information skills development, collection mapping, planning, and evaluation (Williams et al., 2001).

One element of high-quality service is incorporating users' personal needs and expectations into developing programs and services (Millson-Martula & Menon, 1995). According to them, the continued success of a service organization such as an academic library depends on the organization's ability to adjust its products and services to correspond to user needs. Similarly, only customers justify the existence of a library (Hernon & Calvert, 1996).

Public libraries face many different issues in the realm of discovery than those that serve colleges and universities. While academic libraries devote most of their collective resources to scholarly e-journals, public libraries continue to be engaged primarily with books—with e-books representing ever higher levels of interest. The discovery environment for a public library needs the ability to search local print collections, licensed e-book collections, modest collections of scholarly and popular electronic resources, as well as any local repositories of content. In addition to the discovery services oriented to academic and research libraries, various related products and services appeal to different types of libraries. Products oriented to public libraries include, for example, BiblioCommons and AquaBrowser. The online catalog modules of many of the integrated library systems have developed to a point where there is considerable overlap and convergence with discovery interfaces. These online catalog products, though generally tied to the vendor's own ILS products, increasingly offer local indexing capacity, faceted navigation, and integration options with index-based discovery services (Breeding, 2015).

For many organizations, including libraries, Covid-19 has spurred technological trends (Farooq et al., 2021; Rafiq et al., 2021). Covid-19 accelerates academic library technology acceptance and usage among library professionals and users (Rafiq et al., 2021). To slow the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, educational institutions were forced to close their physical library services and make instant migrations to online environments to facilitate remote library users (Fasae et al., 2021; Mishra et al., 2020; Zhou, 2021). Mehta and Wang (2020) identified that the worldwide pandemic has greatly affected library facilities, users, and staff. There was fear and uncertainty while decision-making on the part of the library leadership during the initial pandemic era (Rafiq et al. (2021).

Rafiq et al. (2021) described how the transition from physical to online delivery of information services had affected libraries, especially in the developing world. These libraries face various social, economic, and technological issues due to their lack of wide-scale technological applications, off-campus access to subscribed resources, and a need for more institutional repositories.

The Covid-19 pandemic affects and transforms libraries, services, and management. Libraries must establish infrastructure and improve accessibility to support modern library users who access resources remotely in this rapidly evolving digital environment. Organizational policymakers and library directors should prepare emergency and disaster management plans. The libraries should ensure their presence on social media and use their library websites. To provide broader perspectives about the user's viewpoints about the quality of the resources and services provided by educational libraries, related studies are reviewed (Ashiq et al., 2022).

A survey was carried out by Perera (2005) at the Medical Library of the University of Peradeniya to evaluate the services and the usage of library materials available within the library. Results revealed significant variation within and among user groups concerning various aspects of the study.

Veeramallu et al. (2021) examined user satisfaction with library information resources in Engineering College libraries in Krishna District, in the State of Andhra Pradesh, India. The results revealed that most faculty members of various departments visit the library to borrow books and reference books, and the majority of the respondents have a pleasant feeling about the convenience of library working hours and had a preference for electronic resources because it was much more effective in their teaching and research purposes. Moreover, it was recommended to improve the infrastructural facilities within the library and digitalize the rare collection in the library.

Ogbuiyi and Okpe (2013) evaluated library materials and services in private universities in Nigeria and the degree of user satisfaction with the library materials and perception of services. The results show that 60% of the respondents agreed that the textbooks were adequate, 72% of the respondents agreed that the supply of newspapers in the library was regular, and 59.9 % of respondents accepted that the reference services were perfect.

Amarasekara and Marasinghe (2020) evaluated the users' satisfaction with the main library of the Open University of Sri Lanka to evaluate user satisfaction. The findings showed that the respondents were satisfied with library resources, services, and facilities, while they were not much satisfied with user

awareness programs, training on information searching, dissemination of services through social networking sites, access to WIFI and audiovisual materials, and online library services.

In addition, Mohammed Tukur and Kannan (2020) assessed the faculty member's satisfaction with the information resources and facilities of the three agricultural libraries in Nigeria. It was found that journals, textbooks, thesis, newspapers, technical reports, eBooks, and e-thesis dominated the available information resources in the different agricultural libraries. All types of information resource in print, and digital forms assisted faculty members in meeting their teaching, learning, and research tasks.

Maina et al. (2017) also studied the usage and user satisfaction of library resources at Kisii University Library, Kenya. It was argued that a library should make generous provisions for space and a pleasant atmosphere that would result in high productivity of library staff and library users. The university library staffs and the display boards within the library were the most used ways through which the users could find their needed resources from the library. More of the respondents used library materials daily, and it was recommended that the library be automated and market its resources while providing better training to users.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study assessed the quality of the University of Cebu library facilities, resources, and services and how it leads towards providing quality educational experience among the target-end users. It specifically intends to present the following: 1) profile of the respondents; 2) assessment of the quality of library personnel customer service, facilities, services, and resources and the extent to which it leads to the attainment of the objectives of providing quality education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, environment, respondents, instrument, procedures, treatment of data, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This investigation used the descriptive-survey research design to determine the quality of the University of Cebu Library facilities, resources, and services and how it leads to providing a quality educational experience to the target end-users.

Descriptive research provides a snapshot of the current state of affairs. Correlational research is research designed to discover relationships among variables and to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge (Walinga & Strangor, n.d.).

Research Environment

This investigation was conducted at the University of Cebu-Banilad. It is one of the higher education institutions in Cebu City, which aims to democratize quality education, become a visionary and industry leader, give hope and transform lives. The University of Cebu offers affordable and quality education responsive to the demands of local and international communities.

Research Respondents

The research respondents were the students officially enrolled in the various programs of the university of Cebu-Banilad for the 1st semester of 2022-2023. There were 8,328 students enrolled in the various programs. Using Slovin's formula, the sample size was three hundred eighty-four (384). Inclusion criteria include students officially enrolled in various programs in UC-Banilad during the first semester, S.Y. 2021-2022.

Research Instrument

This research uses the researcher-made survey questionnaire consisting of three (3) parts. The first (1st) part is about the respondent's profile; the second (2nd) part contains items about assessing the library personnel customer service, facilities, services, and resources.

Research Procedures

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Campus Academic Office. The data collection was done using the Google form, in which the link was sent to the various Facebook Messenger accounts of the students.

Treatment of Data

Frequency count and simple percentage were used to analyze the data about the profile of the respondents.

Weighted mean was computed to analyze the data about assessing the quality of facilities, resources, and services provided by the University of Cebu Library Department.

One-Way Anova (Analysis of Variance) was used to determine the significant difference on the respondents' assessment of the quality of personnel customer service, facilities, services, and resources provided by the University of Cebu Library Department.

Ethical Considerations

Moreover, the study was undertaken while minimizing the harm and risks to the research participants. Confidentiality, privacy, and de-identification of research respondents and the data were observed. Respect for person and autonomy was also exercised, and each research participant was asked to read the contents of the consent form before their permission for participants was sought.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section shows the facilities, resources, and services concerning the extent to which it leads to the attainment of the objectives of providing quality education. Table 1 shows the respondents profile in terms of age, gender, and course.

Table 1. Respondents' Profile (n = 384)

Profile	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age		
18-20 years old	301	78.39
21-23 years old	75	19.53
24-26 years old	6	1.56
27-29 years old	1	0.26
30-32 years old	1	0.26
Gender		
Male	91	23.70
Female	293	76.30
Course		
BSA	33	8.59
BSBA	7	1.82
BSHM	61	15.89
BSIT	34	8.85

BSMA	1	0.26
BSN	90	23.44
BSTM	158	41.15

Of the three hundred eighty-four (384) respondents, three hundred one (301), or 78.39%, were aged 18-20 years, while there was only one (1), comprising 0.26%, belonged to the age range of 27 to 29 years old. Also, another one (1), equivalent to 0.26%, belonged to the age range of 30 to 32 years old. These data denote that most of the University of Cebu-Banilad who responded to the study were at the young adulthood stage, where students started to build close connections with others.

Young adults need to form intimate, loving relationships with other people. Success leads to strong relationships, while failure results in loneliness and isolation. This stage covers the early adulthood period when people explore personal relationships (Malone et al. (2016). In Erikson's stage of development, it was believed that people must develop close, committed relationships with other people. Those who are successful at this step will form enduring and secure relationships (Cherry, 2022).

Regarding gender, two hundred ninety-three (293), 76.30%, are females, while ninety-one (91; 23.70%) are males. Based on the records of the University Registrar, the enrollees in the various programs of the University of Cebu-Banilad were ladies.

It is reasonably well known that women today outnumber men in American colleges. In 2003, there were 1.35 females for every male who graduated from a four-year college and 1.3 females for every male undergraduate. Indeed, these female college graduates had a high fertility rate after marriage, being the mothers of the Baby Boom generation. Nevertheless, beginning in the late 1960s and early 1970s, young women's expectations of their future labor force participation changed radically. Rather than follow in their mother's footsteps, they aimed to have careers, not just jobs. These careers were often outside of the traditional female occupations for women. In high school, they took more science and math courses. As a result, their twelfth-grade math and reading test scores increased relative to those of boys (Francis, n.d.).

In the context of the respondents' enrolled course, one hundred fifty-eight (158), or equivalent to 41.15%, were enrolled in the Bachelor of Tourism Management (BSTM) program, while only (1;0.26%) were enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Management Accounting (BSMA) program. During the survey, more BSTM students were willing and immediately responded to the questionnaire administered using Google Links.

While the business world has made great strides in focusing on customer service by studying customers' needs and behaviors, libraries have tended to structure their holdings and services around what they believed was good for their customers. It is the "librarians know best" syndrome, and it is pervasive throughout the profession (Dickstein & Mills, 1997).

Table 2 presents the respondents' assessments on the quality of customer services provided by the University of Cebu-Banilad Library Department personnel.

Table 2. Respondents' Assessments on the Personnel Customer Services (n = 384)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Approachability, courtesy, and accommodation provided by the Library Department staff to the faculty members and students.	3.26	Highly Satisfactory
2. Treatment provided by the Library Department staff to the users.	3.22	Moderately Satisfactory
3. Response, timeliness, and attention provided by Library Department staff to the inquiries/queries of the user.	3.19	Moderately Satisfactory

4. Attitude and demeanor manifested by the Library Department staff in their dealings with the library users.	3.19	Moderately Satisfactory
5. Assistance provided by the Library Department staff to the users for their library resources needs like books, periodicals, & etc.	3.20	Moderately Satisfactory
6. Provision of services to the users by the Library Department staff	3.21	Moderately Satisfactory
7. Manifestation of adequate knowledge and competence in handling the library operation.	3.27	Highly Satisfactory
Weighted Mean	3.22	Moderately Satisfactory

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (Highly Satisfactory); 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Satisfactory); 1.76-2.50 (Less Satisfactory); 1.00-1.75 (Not Satisfactory)

The highest weighted mean of 3.27 indicates that the respondents assessed that the library personnel's manifestation of adequate knowledge and competence in handling the library operation was highly satisfactory. In many cases, the students who used the University library asked assistance from the staff to locate books, journals, magazines, and other learning materials, and they found their service pleasing.

On the opposite, the lowest weighted mean of 3.19 shows that the respondents assessed that the response, timeliness, and attention provided by the University of Cebu-Baniald Library Department staff to the inquiries or queries of the user was moderately satisfactory. This result denotes that, in many cases, the library personnel could answer the students' questions, clarifications, and requests immediately.

Also, another lowest weighted mean of 3.19 indicates that respondents assessed the attitude and demeanor manifested by the Library Department staff in their dealings with the library users as moderately satisfactory. This means that the library personnel exhibited a desirable attitude in attending to the students, especially if they needed assistance in looking for and accessing certain library materials for their course lessons.

The weighted mean of 3.22 denotes that the respondents assessed the quality of library personnel customer services at the University of Cebu-Banilad as moderately satisfactory. It can be gleaned from the preceding statement that students answered that they were happy with the quality of customer services provided by the library staff in many instances.

The concept of service is at the core of the library profession, and the role of libraries in lifelong learning is reiterated to emphasize the importance of quality customer service in libraries (Miao & Wang Bassham, 2007).

Table 3 presents the respondents' assessments on the quality of services provided by the University of Cebu-Banilad Library Department.

Table 3. Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Library Services (n = 384)

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1.	Provision of access to information.	3.17	Moderately Satisfactory
2.	Conduct of library orientation and instruction to the users for effective use of the resources.	3.15	Moderately Satisfactory
3.	Adequacy of opening and operating hours.	3.15	Highly Satisfactory

4.	Availability, appropriateness, and relevance of the library's collection to the curricular needs, updated, relevant and easy to find/locate.	3.16	Moderately Satisfactory
5.	Availability of promotional services to regularly announce new acquisitions.	3.15	Moderately Satisfactory
6.	Availability and maintenance of Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) and indexes to users.	3.17	Moderately Satisfactory
7.	Availability of photocopying services	2.96	Moderately Satisfactory
8.	Provision of assistance by the library personnel to users for the location of reference materials.	3.20	Moderately Satisfactory
9.	Provision of access and functionality of the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC)/KOHA to the various library resources.	3.14	Moderately Satisfactory
10.	Access to the databases (e.g. Electronic Resources like Encyclopedia, Dictionary, Lex Libris)	3.18	Moderately Satisfactory
11.	Provision of In- house index to the subscribed periodicals.	3.14	Moderately Satisfactory
12.	Availability of acquisition list for reference materials to the users.	3.19	Moderately Satisfactory
13.	Availability of table of contents for the users.	3.23	Moderately Satisfactory
14.	Provision of library information file materials (e.g. newspaper clippings)	3.13	Moderately Satisfactory
15.	Provision of library orientations and instructions to the users.	3.16	Moderately Satisfactory
16.	Provision of hand-outs guides, posters, flyers, etc. to the users.	3.09	Moderately Satisfactory
17.	Provision of bulletin and effective means for announcements.	3.20	Moderately Satisfactory
18.	Conduct of library tours to new/freshmen students.	2.96	Moderately Satisfactory
19.	Enough mechanisms for Ask-a-Librarian services (e-mail, and others).	3.07	Moderately Satisfactory
20.	Provision of research consultation(s) to both the faculty and students.	3.16	Moderately Satisfactory
	Weighted Mean	3.14	Moderately Satisfactory

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (Highly Satisfactory); 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Satisfactory); 1.76-2.50 (Less Satisfactory); 1.00-1.75 (Not Satisfactory)

The highest weighted mean of 3.23 indicates that the respondents assessed that the availability of the table of contents for the users was moderately satisfactory. This information denotes that the students who

enter the University library appreciated the control mechanisms implemented by the library and other personnel.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 2.96 shows that the respondents assessed that the conduct of library tours to new or freshmen students was moderately satisfactory. The newly enrolled students of the University of Cebu-Banilad expressed contentment with the activity conducted by library personnel to orient them about the different services and resources that they can use.

The weighted mean of 3.14 denotes that the respondents assessed the quality of library services of the University of Cebu-Banilad as moderately satisfactory. The students find the conduct of library awareness, access to information and databases, assistance and consultations, and Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC/KOHA).

A great deal of learning is associated with using the library, but teachers and librarians still need to be able to capture the evidence of learning (Williams et al., 2001). Williams and Wavell (2001) concluded that several factors outside the library condition the extent to which learning takes place. These influencing factors include interest and enthusiasm shown by members of staff and peers; appropriate and timely intervention to ensure progress can proceed; the foundation of necessary knowledge and skills to proceed; understanding of the individual tasks as well as the main objective of the activity; opportunity to try again and build on understanding; new stimuli, for instance, the use of computers. The focus of several documents is the promotion of reading and how the school library impacts reading development.

Table 4 presents the respondents' assessments on the quality of the facilities of the University of Cebu-Banilad Library Department.

Table 4. Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Library Facilities (n = 384)

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1.	Accessibility of location of the library to users.	3.32	Moderately Satisfactory
2.	Sufficiency of space for library display and library bulletins.	3.22	Moderately Satisfactory
3.	Provision of adequate study area(s)	3.21	Highly Satisfactory
4.	Provision of adequate and comfortable tables and chairs for research works.	3.27	Moderately Satisfactory
5.	Provision of adequate computers and electronic equipment to users.	3.15	Moderately Satisfactory
6.	Availability of printing and photocopying facilities	3.01	Moderately Satisfactory
7.	Availability and provision of Reserve Area.	3.12	Moderately Satisfactory
8.	Access of internet connection for research and other related work.	2.98	Moderately Satisfactory
9.	Provision of wireless are provided to the specific users (Law)	3.10	Moderately Satisfactory
10.	Provision of functional and well-designed furniture and equipment.	3.23	Moderately Satisfactory
11.	Adequacy of lightings and ventilation for conducive environment for studying and reading..	3.30	Moderately Satisfactory
	Weighted Mean	3.17	Moderately Satisfactory

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (Highly Satisfactory); 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Satisfactory); 1.76-2.50 (Less Satisfactory); 1.00-1.75 (Not Satisfactory)

The highest weighted mean of 3.30 indicates that the respondents assessed that the adequacy of lightings and ventilation for conducive environment for studying and reading was moderately satisfactory. This information denotes that the students who used the library expressed that they feel comfort when they studied and do research works University of Cebu-Banilad.

Furthermore, the library climate should help utilize library services. A satisfactory arrangement should be made for the air conditioner. An adequate overview of the client's fulfillment should be completed to decide the estimation of administrations and the region that needs improvement. The library authority ought to coordinate library programs that will give attention to clients on different services rendered in the library. This will help advance the library's picture (Acharya & Kumara, 2022).

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 2.98 shows that the respondents assessed that the access of internet connection for research and other related work was moderately satisfactory. This information shows that the students find satisfaction with the availability of internet accessibility for them to research for their lessons, assignments, and projects.

Furthermore, academic libraries provide a wealth of informational access to library users. In fact, with the advent of online indexes and full-text databases, as well as access to nearly every library and Internet site, students and faculty are more often plagued with too much access rather than insufficient (Stahley & Platt, 2002).

The weighted mean of 3.17 denotes that the respondents assessed that the quality of library facilities of the University of Cebu-Banilad moderately satisfactory. These results show that the students were contended with the location of the library, provision of space chairs and tables for studying, photocopying, internet accessibility, furniture equipment, lightings and ventilation.

As academic libraries renovate or build new spaces that provide services to users, they should consider opportunities to collaborate with other units on campus to develop collaborative services in the new space. These collaborative spaces, such as information commons, teaching and learning centers, and multi-media studios, offer advantages such as providing seamless services to users, leveraging the technology and information expertise of several professional specialties, and pooling resources from more than one campus unit. Careful attention to the planning process is needed in order to ensure mutual understanding of the project goals, responsibilities, resource contributions, and services (Lippincott, 2008).

Table 5 presents the respondents' assessments on the quality of facilities of the University of Cebu-Banilad Library Department.

Table 5. Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Library Facilities (n = 384)

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1.	Availability and variation of library resources, like printed materials and digital materials	3.21	Moderately Satisfactory
2.	Availability and adequacy of the materials in the Circulation Area to user upon request	3.21	Moderately Satisfactory
3.	Control and security measures to safeguard the library and its collection.	3.27	Highly Satisfactory
4.	Availability of reference book collections for utilization to both teachers and students.	3.23	Moderately Satisfactory
5.	Adequacy of collection of posters and maps.	3.14	Moderately Satisfactory
6.	Availability of periodicals collection for utilization	3.15	Moderately Satisfactory
7.	Availability of print resources in the reference and reserve areas as well as newspaper clippings.	3.16	Moderately Satisfactory

8	Availability of electronic resources for faculty members and students.	3.19	Moderately Satisfactory
9	Availability of subscribed online databases to the users (Gale Academic OneFile, Free trials to EBSCO Proquest, etc.)	3.16	Moderately Satisfactory
10.	Availability of thesis, fiction materials, and multimedia collections are available.	3.20	Moderately Satisfactory
Weighted Mean		3.19	Moderately Satisfactory

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (Highly Satisfactory); 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Satisfactory); 1.76-2.50 (Less Satisfactory); 1.00-1.75 (Not Satisfactory)

The highest weighted mean of 3.27 indicates that the respondents assessed that the control and security measures to safeguard the library and its collection of the University of Cebu-Banilad were highly satisfactory. This information denotes that the students who enter the University library appreciated the control mechanisms implemented by the library and other personnel.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.14 shows that the respondents assessed that the adequacy of the collection of posters and maps was moderately satisfactory. This result means that in many instances, the students could use the available printed poster and maps in the library as a reference to their lessons. However, the results denote that their satisfaction with the ideal has a gap, necessitating being addressed by providing up-to-date resources, both in print and digital form.

The weighted mean of 3.19 denotes that the respondents assessed the quality of library resources of the University of Cebu-Banilad as moderately satisfactory. The University students, in many instances, were contented with the quality and quantity of available printed and digital resources like books, newspapers, journals databases, multimedia collections, thesis, and fiction materials since they were able to use these for their research and to add their knowledge relating to the lessons in the courses that they were enrolled.

Libraries have a strategic interest in the tools and technologies that facilitate the discovery of and access to resources for their communities. These tools have seen steady advancement over recent decades, making great strides in the scope and depth of materials addressed and providing library users with ever more convenient ways to access these materials. The progress seen in the successive generations of technology, from online catalogs to metasearch tools, to the current generation of index-based discovery services, represents an incredible improvement. Nevertheless, many gaps remain relative to the potential of universal access to the universe (Breeding, 2015).

Table 5 shows the results of the test of significant differences in the respondents' assessments of the quality of services, facilities, and resources of the University of Cebu-Banilad (UC-Banilad) Library Department.

Table 5. Results on the Test of Significance Difference on the Respondents' Assessments on the Quality of Library Services, Facilities and Resources

Variables	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F statistic	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Evaluation on the Personnel, Services, Facilities & Resources	1.351	3	0.450	1.241	0.293	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant

*Statistically Significant at 0.05 levels

There is a significant difference in the evaluations made by the research respondents on the quality of services, facilities, and resources of the University of Cebu-Banilad (UC-Banilad) Library Department, based on the F-statistic of 1.241, which is higher than the critical value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. These results denote that the students of the different programs had varying perceptions and viewpoints on the state and condition of the available books, periodicals, study areas, Internet connectivity, accession mechanisms, customer service provided by the staff, and the general ambiance of the UC-Banilad Library Department.

Posey (2009) revealed a significant difference in the effect of service mean scores between traditional students aged 22 and younger and non-traditional students aged 23 and older. The effect of service and information control is more critical to non-traditional students aged 23 and older. Also, Cook (2001) disclosed that older age groups scored the library somewhat higher than the younger age groups on the effect of service.

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, the ideal standards of how the library should suffice the learning needs of the University students have gaps with the current state and service provider management of the librarian. These gaps in the state of infrastructures, resources, and customer services call for a more sensible means of devising and implementing courses of action to be at par with global and national norms. Likewise, there should be regular mechanisms for updating the library as the central nerve of learning in an educational institution so that they can respond positively to the needs of 21st-century students amid the presence of technology and digital library resources and databases.

TRANSLATIONAL RESEARCH

Based on the salient findings, an intervention scheme is devised, consisting of a program of actions that gears toward updating and improving the quality of facilities and resources of the University of Cebu-Banilad Library Department. Also, regular evaluation of the satisfaction of the library customer services by the target-end users is an integral part of the scheme.

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